

LINGVOPOETIC PRINCIPLES OF COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LITERARY TEXTS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the scientific-methodological foundations of the linguopoetic principles in the comparative analysis of literary texts. The linguopoetic approach plays a significant role in the deep study of the poetic structure and aesthetic expression means of literary texts. Through the method of comparative analysis, the stylistic dominants, and the alignment of artistic means with national and cultural codes across different texts are analyzed. The article demonstrates how contemporary linguopoetics, as a scientific foundation, enables the understanding of intertextual communication in literary studies.*

Keywords: *Linguopoetics, comparative analysis, literary text, stylistic dominant, poetic structure, aesthetic analysis, cultural context.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada adabiy matnlarni qiyosiy tahlil qilishda lingvopoetik tamoyillarning ilmiy-metodik asoslari muhokama qilinadi. Lingvopoetik yondashuv adabiy matnlarning poetik tuzilmasi va estetik ifoda vositalarini chuqur o'rganishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Qiyosiy tahlil usuli orqali turli matnlardagi stilistik dominantalari, badiiy vositalarning milliy va madaniy kodlar bilan uyg'unligi tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada zamonaviy lingvopoetika ilmiy asos sifatida matnlararo muloqotni anglash imkoniyatini yaratishi ko'rsatilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Lingvopoetika, qiyosiy tahlil, adabiy matn, stilistik dominanta, poetik tuzilmalar, estetik tahlil, madaniy kontekst.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются научно-методологические основы лингвопоэтических принципов в сравнительном анализе литературных текстов. Лингвопоэтический подход играет важную роль в глубоком изучении поэтической структуры и эстетических средств выражения литературных текстов. Через метод сравнительного анализа анализируются стилистические доминанты и соотношение художественных средств с национальными и культурными кодами в разных текстах. В статье показано, как современная лингвопоэтика, как научная основа, позволяет понимать межтекстуальное общение в литературоведении.*

Ключевые слова: *Лингвопоэтика, сравнительный анализ, литературный текст, стилистическая доминанта, поэтическая структура, эстетический анализ, культурный контекст.*

Introduction.

Analyzing literary texts is not only about identifying aesthetic expression means but also about understanding their artistic structure and semantic layers. Especially, the comparative analysis of works from different authors or literary schools through a linguopoetic approach leads to more effective results. Linguopoetics reveals the aesthetic value of a text through the harmony of linguistic units and artistic imagery. This article illuminates the theoretical foundations of this methodology and aims to expand its practical application. Literary text

analysis is one of the most important directions in literary studies, providing the opportunity to deeply understand artistic works, reveal their semantic layers, and assess their aesthetic value. Comparative analysis, on the other hand, serves as a means to reveal the differences and similarities between two or more literary texts. The linguopoetic approach makes it possible to carry out this analysis based on language and aesthetic imagery means. This article presents the role and significance of linguopoetic principles in the comparative analysis of literary texts. The theory of comparative analysis allows a deeper exploration of the structure and semantics of literary texts. This method reveals the individual features of each text, showing that they have unique poetic structures and semantic systems when compared to others.

Linguopoetic principles in this process consider the linguistic characteristics of the analyzed text in harmony with its poetic components. This approach focuses on determining how artistic and aesthetic effects are created through the linguistic means of a text. Linguopoetics, as a discipline situated between language and literature, plays an essential role in analyzing the semantic structure of literary texts. The poetic structure of an artistic work is revealed through the harmony of lexical, syntactic, phonetic, and stylistic means. The linguopoetic approach studies these means not just as grammatical units but as elements that create aesthetic meaning. Therefore, conducting a comparative literary analysis based on linguopoetic principles allows for a profound examination of a text not only in terms of content but also from the perspectives of form and expression means.

The goal of linguopoetic analysis is to determine how the author integrates different language units — such as words, word combinations, grammatical forms, or syntactic structures — into the creation of a literary text, and to show how the unique harmony of these units achieves a particular aesthetic effect.[1] In the comparative analysis of literary texts, the first task is to examine the artistic expression power of the language. Through linguistic means, images, metaphors, epithets, parallel constructions, and other poetic elements are created, which determine the text's aesthetic impact. The linguopoetic approach analyzes each of these elements, uncovering the functional load they bring to the text. In this case, comparative analysis focuses on how poetic means are applied differently or similarly across two or more texts, and to what extent they serve the artistic aesthetic purpose.

It should be noted that, despite its universal characteristics, linguistic stylistic analysis cannot fully encompass the unique features of literary texts. Analyzing such texts requires a deep understanding of the author's ideological intent, worldview, aesthetic position, artistic thinking style, and relationship to cultural-philological traditions.[2] A.A.Lipgart also contributed to the development of the linguopoetic concept system. According to him, linguopoetics is a branch of philology that studies stylistically marked language units used in literary texts in relation to their function and their role in conveying specific ideological-aesthetic content and creating an aesthetic impact.[3] Furthermore, linguopoetic principles include the analysis of the structural elements of the text. This involves studying the poetic functions of linguistic units such as sentence construction, syntactic parallelism, inversion, ellipsis, and gradation. Special attention is paid to the alignment of these units with national cultural codes when conducting comparative studies of texts from different literary traditions. Through such analysis, the stylistic choices of each author, their artistic intentions, and aesthetic goals are revealed more clearly.

When using the term "lingvopoetika," it should be remembered that it can refer to two directions, i.e., to express opposing types of research. One of these involves identifying thematic-stylistic characteristics of artistic style means applied in a specific work or group of works. Researches such as those of Z.B. Eshmambetova belong to this category. In her studies,

she examines the relationship between the author's speech and the character's speech as a linguopoetic problem and attempts to apply linguopoetic analysis to works in the dramatic genre.[4] Linguopoetic comparative analysis also relies on cultural context. Each literary text is created within a particular socio-historical, cultural, and aesthetic environment. Therefore, the differences and similarities between texts are expressed not only at the language and style levels but also in their semantic-spiritual layers. Comparative analysis based on linguopoetic principles serves to reveal these layers. As a result, the reader not only understands the structure of the text but also senses the aesthetic views, the author's position, and social messages behind it.

A.Yu.Morozov's dissertation is particularly noteworthy. The novelty of this work lies in the three-level method of text analysis, i.e., linguopoetic analysis methodology, which was previously only applied to the study of artistic texts. Here, for the first time, it is applied to the language of advertising texts. The research discusses the expansion of the application scope of linguopoetic analysis methodology and its application to not only literary but also other types of texts.[5] Another crucial principle in the linguopoetic comparative analysis of literary texts is the identification of the stylistic dominant. The stylistic dominant is the primary stylistic means that defines the overall artistic tone of the text. Through it, other poetic elements of the text are systematized, and their contribution to the artistic goal is assessed. Comparative analysis identifies how the stylistic dominant is determined in each text and what poetic system it creates. It should be noted that using linguopoetic principles as the basis for comparative analysis facilitates the study of texts from different periods, literary schools, and genres together. This method allows for the identification of changes in the poetic thinking level, artistic expression means, and aesthetic principles across texts. Particularly in modern literature, this approach is invaluable for identifying poetic innovations.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, conducting comparative analysis of literary texts based on linguopoetic principles enables a deep scientific analysis in literary studies. This method reveals the aesthetic tone, stylistic dominants, poetic structure, and semantic layers of each text. Linguopoetic analysis also considers cultural, social, and ideological contexts, helping to reveal the intertextual aesthetic communication between texts. Therefore, linguopoetic comparative analysis is recognized as an effective scientific approach widely applied in contemporary literary research.

REFERENCES

1. Задорнова В.Я. Словеснохудожественное произведение на разных языках как предмет лингвопоэтического исследования. Автореф. дисс. ... докт. филол. наук. М., 1992. С. 19; 49с.
2. Akhmanova O., Zadornova V. On Linguopoetic Stratification of Literary Text // *Poetica. An International Journal of LinguisticLiterary Studies*. Tokyo, 1977. №7. P. 50–60.
3. Липграт А.А. Лингвопоэтическое исследование художественного текста: теория и прагматика (на материале английской литературы 1620 веков). Дисс. ... докт. фи лол. наук. М., 1996. С. 23.
4. Ешмамбетова З.Б. Соотношение авторской речи и речи персонажа как лингвопоэтическая проблема (на материале английского языка). Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. М., 1984.
5. Морозов А.Ю. Выразительные возможности рекламного текста (на материале американской рекламы). Автореф. дисс. ... канд. филол. наук. М., 2001.